

FAIR Ontologies for Cataloguing AI Risks

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The EU's AI Act (AIA) has brought AI risks and impacts into sharp focus based on the need to balance economic progress with potential impacts on people's health, safety, and fundamental rights. The envisaged way for achieving this balance is through an ongoing risk management process that identifies, evaluates, and mitigates AI risks and impacts. This process requires well-documented information regarding the AI system, its context of use, risks, impacts, and mitigation measures. What makes these processes complex are the uncertainties around the use of AI and emergence of new risks as the field progresses. A Catalogue of risks and impacts associated with development and use of AI assists AI developers, providers, and users in addressing these complexities. Using ontologies for cataloguing risks in a FAIR manner (i) enables easy access to AI risk and impact information, (ii) assists in sharing this information between different entities in the AI value chain, (iii) facilitates integration with existing risk management processes, and (iv) enables reuse and enhancement of the ontology by different stakeholders over time. Additionally, an AI risk catalogue as a linked data resource can facilitate documentation within risk management systems through use of machine-readable formats and automation towards identification of existing risk-impact patterns. In this talk, I will present our ongoing work on development of FAIR risk taxonomies and ontologies based on EU regulations and international standards.

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